

BIODIVERSITY AND SOME MIGRATORY BIRDS OF THE BUKHARA OASIS

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The nature of the globe varies greatly from geographical to ecological, with mountains, plains, deserts, seas, oceans and rivers in the animal and plant world, which differ greatly from each other in their diversity depending on the climate and natural conditions in which they live.

Bukhara region is located in the southeastern region of the republic and is distinguished by its diverse nature and seasonal beauty.

Biodiversity refers to the diversity of all life on Earth, including animals, plants, microorganisms, their genes and ecosystems. The term "biodiversity" does not reflect biological information about a particular organism, but the interaction between all parts of the biological world.

Reservoirs (reservoirs, lakes, fish ponds), formed in recent years on the territory of the republic for various purposes, not only play an important role in increasing its economic potential, but also are the main space for the formation of fauna of waterfowl and near-water birds associated with life in local regions. This, of course, acquires great scientific and practical importance for the conservation of species biodiversity in our republic.

But the "bird flu", which in recent years has caused great problems and disappointments around the world, N1 N1-swine flu, is the main mediator in the penetration of a number of problems, such as the spread of worm diseases and radiation exposure among fish species raised on fish farms, including migratory birds. This requires in-depth studies of the ecology of migratory birds living in reservoirs and terrestrial biotopes.

The main idea put forward in our research work is that by analyzing the ornithological situation in the waters forming and forming in the desert zone of the central and south-western regions of the republic, and the surrounding terrestrial biotopes, the species composition of birds can penetrate into the regions through bird migration, studying the timing and direction of migrations,

the nature of the occurrence of species in the respective areas, as well as the observed changes in their biology, is to prevent problems that may arise.

The data obtained during our observations determine the species composition, number, flight path and the main areas of concentration of the avifauna of the region by seasons of the year: spring and autumn migration, wintering, as well as nesting seasons. The role of ponds and terrestrial biotopes in the life of migrating species is analyzed; the main conditions attracting migrating species in the territory are studied.

A calendar of migrating species is compiled based on the timing of their migration, a marked map of migration centers is compiled, on the basis of which it is possible to carry out measures to control the number of migratory birds in order to prevent certain problems that may arise through migratory birds.

Along with the schultz, by determining the migration routes of migratory birds, infectious diseases are prevented from entering the territory of our republic, and the main concentration centers of small and rare bird species among migratory birds are determined, opportunities for organizing their protection in these territories are born.

In the course of our observations, it was found that wintering and early-arriving birds in the region do not spread across all lakes within the same norm. Denizkul partially lakes Zikri, Karakir, Zamanbobo and Oek-Agitma serve as the main places of birds gathering. As we noted above, these landscapes are constantly changing depending on winter temperatures.

In the years when the winter cold comes (2007-2018-2023), there is a regular accumulation of birds in lakes with extensive open spaces and close food sources at a distance of 700-1000 meters from the shore, forming from 1000 to 7000 clusters. Initially, these clusters included mallards, chocks, and red ducks, and in the last days of the month this diversity is enriched by such birds as diamond ducks, suckers, coots.

Currently, thousands of pairs of large Cormorants nest and breed in the reed thickets around Aydarkul, on the islands. Since small cormorants are found on the lake almost at any time of the year, small cormorants also nest in these territories. Small cormorant-phalacrocorax pygmaeus (Pallas, 1773). He belongs to the order of mallards. By status, it is close to the vulnerable, breeding and wintering, Southwestern Palearctic species listed in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3 (NT) and the red list of the International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) (LR-NT). The main distribution areas of the small cormorant in Uzbekistan include the watersheds

of the Aral Sea, the middle and lower reaches of the Amu Darya, the Kashkadarya basin, and the middle reaches of the Syr Darya.

Nesting and wintering are noted in these places. It is protected in the waters of Sudoche, Tuzkan, Karakyr, Lake Dengizkul of the republic. The whooper swan (Linnaeus, 1758).

The swan is a species from the duck family of the order geese. By status weak, rare, listed in the Red Book of Uzbekistan 2 (Vu:P), a Northern Palearctic species. By the nature of occurrence in Uzbekistan, it refers to migratory and wintering species. It occurs on flat reservoirs and flights in the southern part of the Aral Sea, winters on the Southern Surkhandarya reservoir, lakes Tuzkan and Aidar.

Spring migration is observed in February-April, Autumn-in October, November. The wintering period falls on December, February. During this period, they like areas of large reservoirs where dense vegetation grows. Sibilant swans feed on algae and aquatic invertebrates in ponds. Hunting is prohibited. It is protected in nature reserves created on the watersheds of Sudoche, Karakyr, Tuzkon, Deniz-Kul. We are conducting research work on the migration of birds in the territory of Uzbekistan in various seasonal periods. The biodiversity of migratory and migrating birds of Uzbekistan is also being studied.

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